

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 7.1 Consent Forms Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Coordination and Support Action (2014-2020) under grant agreement No. 101021669

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable reference number	D7.1
Deliverable name	Consent Forms
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package contributing to the deliverable	WP7
Due date	31.5.2021
Version	
Actual submission date	28.5.2021

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DOCUMENT CHANGE CONTROL

Version	Date	Status	Author(s), reviewer	Description
0.1	01/05/21	Draft	Tuomas Tammilehto	Initial Draft
0.2	24/05/21	Draft	Rashel Talukder	Review
0.3	24/05/21	Draft	Tuomas Tammilehto	Minor corrections/clarifications according to the feedback from the review are added.
0.4	24/05/21	Draft	Marco Gercke	Review
1.0	28/05/21	Final	Rashel Talukder	Final review, approval and submission

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Summary

Consent is an absolute requirement for both ethically sound project and its outcomes. Thus, this document, Deliverable D7.1.1, describes in details a so-called *Consent Form Template* and the related *Information Sheet Template* that instructs on how to make the different detailed consent forms for the various activities of CYCLOPES. This deliverable also gives guidance on from whom consent is needed not forgetting presenting the important background and related legislation.

Introduction

As a given requirement, all activities which involves human participation must ensure respect for people and for human dignity, thus, protection of the freedoms, rights and interests of the research participants is of paramount significance. Above is imperative: all activities of CYCLOPES must comply with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law.

Since, CYCLOPES activities involve human beings during e.g. interviews, questionnaires, surveys, workshops etc. specific attentions has put to ensure above. The participants of CYCLOPES activities will be healthy adults, largely from within the consortium but also invited CYCLOPES substance matter experts from e.g. the law enforcement community.

Therefore, it is imperative to establish informed consent procedures and guarantee the following:

- The participation is voluntary, and anyone has the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw the participation at any time, without consequences.
- An Information sheet with all the necessary information on nature, purpose and requirements to participation will be distributed prior to the participation, written in a language and in terms that can be easily and fully understood (if the information required for understanding consent is not adequately disclosed in the consent form itself), and
- A Consent form, written in comprehensible and understandable language and terms, completed and made available to participant. Further, it is important to ensure that potential participants are not pressured or coerced into giving consent.

The CYCLOPES Consortium, fully respecting human dignity and value will, hence, establish and implement informed consent procedures for human participation in its activities, and also ensure that participants who contribute their time, insights, effort and data for the use of our project will only be allowed to participate after they have provided voluntarily and freely informed consents.

At all events, the CYCLOPES project will provide guidance and steering on legal, ethical, policy and societal issues as well as on so-called traditional research ethics, including of course the involvement of humans in the project.

Therefore, and also according to the Description of Action (DoA)¹, this deliverable – *D7.1.1 Consent Forms* – a result of the task *T7.1 entitled Legal and Ethical Issue Guidance to Consortium Partners During Project Implementation* (part of Work Package 7), has a goal to

¹ CYCLOPES, Description of Action (DoA), Part A, p. 37.

provide the necessary guidance to the consortium partners, to allow each to conduct project activities in accordance to legal and ethical regulations. This work includes the development of various templates, as well as actionable ethical and legal guidance that will support consortium members during the process of carrying out work and preparing deliverables.

This deliverable is to establish guidelines for seeking so-called Healthy Consent – a routinized process needed to ensure ethical and legal compliance. The objective is achieved through the *Consent Form Template* and *Information Sheet Template* that supports the creation of detailed consent forms needed in this CYCLOPES projects' activities, for example, surveys, interviews, training events, workshops etc.

Thus, in this document, will be introduces the key definitions and different terms and concepts important for both understanding consent and its need in H2020 projects (many of them will be in the footnotes). In addition, as stated above, this deliverable illustrates the *Consent Form Template* and *Information Sheet Template*, i.e. models to be followed when creating various consent forms for different purposes during the lifecycle of the CYCLOPES project. Further, this deliverable also informs on from whom consent needs to be requested.

Understanding Consent: the Principles

Consent for Participating in Various Activities

Consent has been for long an integral part of any research that involves human participants, especially of course in research that infringe someone's bodily integrity, for example in medical research. This principle has been unfortunately sometimes neglected, and in few extreme cases with very catastrophic outcomes. For example, during the Nazi regime when Josef Mengele committed heinous atrocities in the name of science. Thus, maybe the question of consent was a major subject during the Nuremberg Trials, and as an outcome of those, so-called, Nuremberg Code was formulated to clarify and stress its importance. For example, the Article 1 of the Nuremberg Code² on voluntary consent requires that the person giving consent:

“should have sufficient knowledge and comprehension of the elements of the subject matter involved, as to enable him to make an understanding and enlightened decision. This latter element requires that, before the acceptance of an affirmative decision by the experimental subject, there should be made known to him the nature, duration, and purpose of the experiment; the method and means by which it is to be conducted; all inconveniences and hazards reasonably to be expected; and the effects upon his health or person, which may possibly come from his participation in the experiment” (Nuremberg Military Tribunal 1947).

This characterisation has been updated since many times to accommodate different research fields, but the main elements are all relevant today. For example, the definition of Informed Consent, given in the Directive 2001/20/EC relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, defines informed consent as follows:

“Informed Consent is the decision, which must be written, dated and signed, to take part in a clinical trial, taken freely after being duly informed of its nature, significance, implications and risks and appropriately documented, by any person capable of giving

² For more details, see Katz J. The Nuremberg Code and the Nuremberg Trial: A Reappraisal. *JAMA*. 1996; 276 (20):1662–1666. doi:10.1001/jama.1996.03540200048030.

consent or, where the person is not capable of giving consent, by his or her legal representative; if the person concerned is unable to write, oral consent in the presence of at least one witness may be given in exceptional cases, as provided for in national legislation.”

This latter is adopted for CYCLOPES project guiding principle, although the stress is on the “informed and free decision”, since that is more pivotal than the means to record the consent. In many cases, for example, active involvement in a workshop or answering to a survey by a healthy adult can be interpreted as a consent, and missing a written statement can be overlooked. Nevertheless, the firm intention of CYCLOPES is to have written consent forms from all participants of every research event.

Consent is imperative from different point-of-views, not least when thinking different ethical principles of research. The first principle is related with **respecting people** and with the fact that people should be treated as **autonomous**. This means that persons should be able to make their own decisions about what to do and what to agree to. Therefore, researchers (and others carrying the activities in this project) must respect that individuals make their own informed decisions about whether to participate in the activities. Thus, in order to treat people as autonomous, individuals must be provided with complete information about their participation, and let them decide on their own whether to participate or not.³

The relevant information related with research activities such as interviews and surveys, i.e. those envisaged in CYCLOPES, includes description of the activities, what the participation means in practice, how long it takes etc.

Above presented principle results to the following bare minimum of the information on the consent form and information sheet:

- the contact details of the person responsible for the activity;
- the activity subject and/or topic;
- description of the (concrete) data collection methods (i.e. how the information will be collected: via interview, survey...), and how long the collection will take (e.g. filling this survey will take ca. 15 minutes...);
- the purpose for the collection of the material, how the material it is stored and used, as well as the possible further use of the material; and
- voluntary nature of the participation.

Further, the participants of any events should be given an opportunity to ask questions about the activity and/or their role. Therefore, the organiser of the event should be prepared to answer to questions on the following topics (if not include the answers into the consent form and/or information sheet to begin with):

³ It must be remembered that, for example, young children, people who are very ill, or those with mental disabilities might not have the capacity to make fully informed decisions about what they do or what happens to them. Since, they cannot make a true informed decision on their own, in these cases, people should be protected, and be included in research only under specific circumstances. In the case of CYCLOPES, the activities are done solely with healthy adults who are able to understand their participation and can express their will. Thus, this point is more of a reminder of the complexity of life and ethics than anything else.

- Deeper information on the activity, e.g. scientific purpose, detailed information on the methodology, research questions, paradigm etc.
- Information on how the data (especially possible confidential material) will be safeguarded, and where the material will be achieved after the activity is done.
- Information on possible publications or other outcomes of the activity and their expected time scale.

And of course, consent is a requirement in the consent form too. This somewhat tautological phrase means, that the consent must be explicitly asked in the form. Also, the autonomy of the participants means that they have the right to stop their participation at any time, and without giving any explanation or justification. This must be expressed in the consent form too.

The second principle could be phrased as “**do no harm**” (mental or physical), and is related with the aim of doing research for a **purpose of (greater) good and help the society**. Research or any other activities should never hurt anyone or find out information at the expense of other. Of course, there are occasions when this cannot always be achieved. For example, giving a vaccination during a medical experiment can hurt, and there might be harmful side effects. However, the obligation is to do the best to minimise the possible risks and to maximise the benefits for participants; in the case of a new vaccination, the intended outcome surpass small inconvenience. Therefore, explaining the risks but also the benefits must be included into the consent process. In practice, they need to be expressed in the consent form and/or in a separate information sheet to be handed to the participants.

In the activities of CYCLOPES, mental or psychological harm are not envisaged. In addition, possible harm caused by monetary loss when participating to the events is hardly relevant.

The third principle is about **justice and fairness**. When conducting anything that involves human participation, starting from recruitment of participants to choosing the location of the events, all should be reflected critically, thinking especially who benefits from the research activities, and who bears the risks. The answers tells us much about what is fair and just, and to whom. For example, decision about who are included in research activities should not be made based on accessibility, availability, or on the assumption that someone is less able to decline his/her participation.

In regards to CYCLOPES, the question of fairness is not necessarily an issue, since the participants are partners and/or other stakeholders of the project who are contributing toward a common achievement (expressed in various documents of the project, including the DoA). also much of the participation is based on the participants own desire to contribute to the project. Nevertheless, fairness must be kept in mind, so that the results of the project will not have any biases resulting from the selection of participants, if and when they are not done based on need and appropriateness but rather (solely) on convenience.

When thinking the consent and process of acquiring it, i.e. the consent form and related material, this third principle materialise itself as a simple, readable and understandable form that does not exclude anyone with its appearance, content, language, and/or layout.

Yet another important principle is **privacy and data protection**. These has been stressed in research for very long, and are actually somewhat overlapping in intertwined with the other principles presented above. Privacy and data protection will be dealt in more details in the next chapter.

Consent for the Use of Personal Data

During the recent years, the European Union has been very active on privacy and on the use of personal data too, not least with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that came into effect in May 2018.⁴ However, it must be noted that respecting people's privacy and securing data are not only legal matters, but an ethical issues related with research. Privacy is both a fundamental right on its own, but also an important research principle.

In regards to privacy protection, data protection of personal data is the most critical, and it must be applied during the gathering and collecting of the data, processing the data⁵, and when publishing the data. Consent is thus aside from giving permission for participating to research activities, also one possible legal basis for processing personal data. Consent gives the data subjects the opportunity to monitor the processing of their personal data and influence it by withdrawing their consent. The requirements for consent to personal data are much same as for consent for research purposes: to be valid, it must be an informed, freely given, and unambiguous indication of the data subject's⁶ wishes.

Thus, data subjects can give their consent for predefined, specific and lawful purposes. If the purpose of processing personal data changes, one needs to ask for a new consent before starting processing.

Personal data is any data that relates to a directly or indirectly identifiable natural person⁷; such data could include direct or indirect (secondary/linkable) identifier of a person).⁸ Direct identifier can include, for example:

- name; surname, home address, email address (name.surname@company.com) identification number; location data; and online identifier such IP/MAC address, cookie ID, the advertising identifier of a person's mobile phone.
- National ID/passport number
- Data held by a hospital or doctor, which could be a symbol that uniquely identifies a person.
- Physical/behavioural attributes: e.g., shape/colour/markings/distinguishing feature of face/any body part (e.g. hair/eye colour, birthmark, voice, gait etc.).

⁴ GDPR is available online at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&qid=1622194093775&from=EN> For more details, see for example <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>

⁵ This includes any automated or manual operation involving capturing collecting, recording, organising, structuring, storing, adapting, altering, transferring, erasing/destroying/deleting of (personal) data.

⁶ Data-subject is any identified or identifiable natural person whether their data is already processed or not. For example, a person is a data-subject already even when although they are merely being contacted to consider signing a consent form to permit the use of specific personal data of theirs for a particular purpose and context of processing over a specific period – because they have been identified and similarly when they are invited to participate in a workshop and/or act as an advisor etc. they are a data-subject by virtue of having been identified even if the extent of processing their data may have been simply to emailed them.

⁷ Natural person refers to any individual who is alive. This term is used in contradistinction to a legal person (a company/organisation/enterprise) or a deceased person, the information about either of whom is not considered to be personal data.

⁸ See for example Article 29 Working Party Opinion 4/2007 on the concept of personal data

- NB! Other factors can identify an individual (the above is a non-exhaustive list). Other elements of data that can directly identify an individual is personal data although processing any (potential) identifier of an individual would not in itself mean that the Data Controller⁹ is processing personal data because the purpose and context of processing of any elements of personal data is crucial to determining whether personal data is being processed.¹⁰

Especially careful one must be with so-called Special Category Data. This is sensitive personal data, including:

- genetic data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics;
- healthcare data (physical, mental health status and healthcare services used);
- biometric data to uniquely identify a natural person (including facial images, fingerprint, gait);
- racial or ethnic origin;
- political, religion, philosophical opinions and/or beliefs;
- religious or philosophical beliefs;
- trade union membership;
- sex life or sexual orientation; and
- information about any criminal history.

As a rule, the processing of personal data belonging to special categories is prohibited. Thus, it should not be collected in the first place. However, special categories of personal data can be processed by virtue of the GDPR in the following cases:

When,

- the data subject has given his or her explicit consent for the processing of the personal data in question;
- the processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or another person if the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent.
- the personal data is processed in the course of the legitimate activities of a foundation, association or any other not-for-profit body with a political, philosophical, religious or trade union aim and the processing is appropriately protected. Such processing may only relate to members or former members of the body or to persons who have regular contact with it in connection with its purposes. Data may not be disclosed outside that body without the consent of the data subjects.

⁹ Data Controller is the entity (person/organisation) who determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data. A Data Controller could be i) public organisation/NGO, ii) a research institution, iii) a private company/enterprise. The purpose of a Data Controller would be typically related to their role and responsibilities which mainly could be distinguished as falling under the two categories of “social/public-duty, not-for-profit” objectives or “business, marketing” objectives.

¹⁰ If another entity (person/organisation) than the Data Controller is processing data on Data Controller’s behalf, they are called Data Processors.

- the processing relates to personal data which are manifestly made public by the data subject, such as by publishing them on the data subject's own website.
- the processing is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

Processing is also permitted whenever courts are acting in their judicial capacity.

In the following cases, processing is not possible by virtue of the GDPR alone, but requires more specific regulations or other procedures.

When processing is necessary,

- for the purposes of carrying out the obligations and exercising specific rights of the controller or of the data subject in the field of employment and social security and social protection law in so far as it is authorised by Union or Member State law or a collective agreement pursuant to Member State law. Measures for safeguarding the fundamental rights and benefits of the data subject must also be stipulated in this connection.
- for reasons of substantial public interest, on the basis of Union or Member State law. The regulations that permit processing shall be proportionate to the aim pursued and respect the essence of the right to data protection. Measures for safeguarding the fundamental rights and benefits of the data subject must also be stipulated in this connection.
- for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of Union or Member State law or pursuant to contract with a health professional. Such processing requires that the data is only processed by a professional or person subject to a statutory obligation of secrecy.
- for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, on the basis of Union or Member State law which also provides for measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy.
- for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with the GDPR and based on Union or Member State law. The regulations that permit processing shall be proportionate to the aim pursued and respect the essence of the right to data protection. Measures for safeguarding the fundamental rights and benefits of the data subject must also be stipulated in this connection.

CYCLOPES does not expect to collect any Special Category Data, but it is vital to know this in case it becomes relevant.

Summary of the Principles

As a summary, relevant to CYCLOPES it is pivotal to acknowledge that the individuals who are participating to any research events have the right to do so voluntarily, as it is voluntary to give one's personal data. These must be specifically requested. The participants also have the right to decline without any consequences. This latter point is especially important when the

individuals are in a subordinate position (employer-employee, student-professor), and thus this needs to be well addressed. This case is perhaps challenging in CYCLOPES when, for example, request for participation for a survey or an interview are asked from individuals in hierarchical organisations such as

- The participants can also refuse to continue to participate at any time, also without any consequences (however, the data that the participant has produced/given to that point can be used).
- The participants can revoke their participation altogether, and this should be made as easy as giving the consent.
- The participants are entitled to know about the content of the research; how their personal data is used; how the research is carried out, for example, on practicalities; how the data is handled, stored and achieved.
- Also important is that the participants have a sufficient knowledge on the aims of the research, as well as on possible risks and harm that participating can cause. Benefits too, are important to disclose.
- All this information must be given (in written whenever possible) in a comprehensive manner. The organisers of the event must reply to participants possible questions, and give enough time to go through the information, so that the participants can make a well-informed and rational decision.

Before going to the details of the *Consent Form Template* and *Information Sheet Template* there is still one issue to discuss: the participants themselves. This might be a bit out of scope of the topic of this deliverable, however, few words needs to be said. Thus, in the next short chapter will present the principles relating to the people envisaged to take part in CYCLOPES activities, and how that effects the necessities for consent.

The Participants

Participants in Research Events

CYCLOPES aims to engage only with so-called healthy adults, thus the consent form and the information sheet is designed not take into account e.g. underage participants or participants with disabilities affecting their mental capacity. In other word, CYCLOPES avoids recruiting those who for any reason may be, or may feel, vulnerable, and for those selected, providing prior information about the extent and nature of any processing covering the requirements in Article 13/14 including Explicit Consent Article 6.1(a), 9.2(a) and 22(1) (b) for profiling strictly for research purposes that will have no legal effect whatsoever on the participants.

Participants in Project Management and Administrative Activities

The baseline is that CYCLOPES process the absolute minimum of personal data within the consortium for the purpose of the necessary communication, administration and project management. These tasks should be proceed without the requirement for explicit consent.

This is because processing of the minimum of personal data such as emails, address and affiliation could be readily seen as essential for the implementation and management of the project for which all the partners share the signed contract, including data protection obligation,

and thereby are committed to cooperation in the joint endeavour which requires the mutual ability to use such minimum of personal data to support communication and management of the project.

Such processing of data within the consortium does not extend to the use of any personal data that falls outside the definition of “legitimate use for the conduct of the project and its management”. In particular, it does not extend to the use of sensitive personal data such as special category data as defined by GDPR – irrespective of whether it is limited to project partners or not.

It must be noted, that the minimum use of personal data (e.g. email, address, organisational affiliation etc.) for legitimate purpose presented above also extends to any project advisors, potential advisors, specific external collaborators, who by virtue of either having already signed a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA), Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), (or indeed the Consent Form itself), or being already known to one of the partners, and for that reason would be legitimately contactable by the members of the consortium specifically for purposes related to the project. Further, the use of the essential minimum of personal data extends too for the purpose of merely inviting data-subjects established as candidates to participate in different meetings etc. by virtue of having a specific expertise and role, and having been selected a such as a potential participant for a role for which they can subsequently be invited to consider signing a consent form, naturally given all the required project information.

Instructions for Consent Form and Information Sheet

When drafting and creating the Consent Form and the related Information Sheet (whether online or off line) one must ask several pivotal questions starting from why the consent is needed into perhaps more mundane who is the right contact person.

The following questions are put here to guide the work. In addition, the different elements of the consent forms are listed and explained here below.

The most obvious and critical thing in any consent is to evaluate whether the informed consent form contains adequate information to meet the necessary requirements.

In most cases, an Information Sheet should be provided together with the Consent Form. In other cases, the information can be put in the same document (e.g. one pdf file). In any case, critical is that the person who gives his/her consent has understood why and for what he/she has given it.

Thus typically, the Information Sheet, will include details in a question-answer format such as:

- Who is organising and funding the activities;
- The purpose and the duration of the project;
- The type of the specific activity in which the participant is invited to participate (e.g. interview, questionnaire, training);
- The purpose of the specific activity in which the participant is invited to participate;
- The reasons/criteria for which the participant is invited to participate;
- Where this activity takes place;

- The duration of the activity (how many times and for how long the participant will be occupied);
- Any foreseeable risk, discomfort or disadvantages;
- Any benefits to the participant or to others which may be reasonably expected from the activity;
- How any incidental findings will be treated;
- The voluntary character of the participation;
- The opportunity of the participant to ask questions and to withdraw at any time from the activity without consequences;
- The detailed procedures adopted for ensuring data protection (a separate information sheet for data processing will be drafted in case of processing of personal data by the data controller);
- The contact details of the activity organiser (legal person responsible for the research activity and natural person acting as contact point);
- What will happen with the information provided by the participant at the end of the activity period;
- What will happen to the results of the activities.

All above should be present in the CYCLOPES Information Sheet/Consent Form.

Critical too, is the way how the consent is collected and documented. Thus, a written form is required. The form needs to be written in an understandable style in known language to the participants. The form should include questions to which the participants are asked to answer with a clear “yes” or “no” -options.

The questions are as follows:

- I have read the information on this activity, i.e. the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] that will be carried out as part of Task <Task number and title> of the H2020 CYCLOPES project.
- My questions about the activity have been answered to my satisfaction, and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point.
- I understand that I am free to withdraw from the activity at any time without giving a reason for my withdrawal without any consequences to my future treatment by the activity organiser.
- I agree to provide information to the activity organiser under the conditions set out here and/or in the Information Sheet.
- I have been reassured that after analysis of the minimum information sought and processed, any personal data of mine shall be fully protected and deleted after the conclusion of the study.

- I consent to the information collected for the purposes of this activity, once anonymized/pseudonymised / de-identified/de-linked / (re)identified¹¹ (so that I cannot be identified), to be used for any other purposes related to the CYCLOPES project.
- I wish to participate in the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] under the conditions set out here and/or in the Information Sheet.

The participants will also fill in their name, signature, date of consent, and contact details.

The researcher and/or organiser of the event will include their names and details to the Consent Form and/or related Information Sheet, too

In the Consent Form and/or related Information Sheet, it must be communicated too that the personal information included in the consent form is processed in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation¹², and must be stored securely for the time period mentioned in articles 36.1 of the CYCLOPES Grant Agreement (4 years after the completion of the project) for accountability reasons. Consequently, the organiser of the activity must follow this practice too.

The Consent Form Template and Information Sheet Template

In this Chapter are presented the two templates, i.e. examples of the Consent Form and Information Sheet for CYCLOPES project. They serve as general guidance to help the structuring the forms consistent with relevant GDPR requirements for consent seeking for interviews surveys, workshop activities etc.¹³ As such, the templates have perhaps more extensive structure than the actual consent forms derived from them. The templates are subjects to updates in case of any new purpose and contexts of data processing may arise or simply to continuously improve the form based on feedback from the consortium members.

It is imperative that in the forms is explained why the participants are invited to the research purposes as well as the legal basis of any automatic data capture (if included in the study).

Also important is notifying of any transfer of data to any other entities including in particular to organisations in Third Countries (without data protection provisions deemed equivalent to EC) and the rights to ensure full transparency on the basis of an Informed Consent Process as mandated by the GDPR must be explained, fully, clearly and specifically.

For example, if the objectives of the research activity are in the public interest and compliant with Art. 6.1.e GDPR or Art. 9.2.J in accordance with Art. 89 9(1) to respect the essence of the

¹¹ Anonymization refers to the process of transforming the data, either reversibly or irreversibly, into a string as an encrypted structure. De-identification/De-linking is to transform a personal data element, almost always reversibly, such that it is not possible to readily link the data to an individual although through authorised/unauthorised access to the code used for the transformation or by combining other elements of data (which are not de-identified) the person could be identified. (Re)Identifying is to identify a person by combining elements of personal data, some of which may have been pseudonymised/masked to some extent to render them de-identified.

¹² Particularly the Art. 6 on the lawfulness of processing data, especially “processing of personal data is, in summary lawful: a) with consent of the data subject”, but also Art. 13 Information to be provided where personal data are collected from the data subject, and Art. 14 Information to be provided where personal data have not been obtained from the data subject.

¹³ Especially Art. 6.1.a GDPR, Recital (40)-(43), information to be provided: Art. 13, Art.14.

right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the “data-subject”, the type of data that we seek through the questionnaire / interview / workshop is needed for usage over the lifecycle of the project and for long enough afterwards to support follow-on research as deemed essential.

Further, to support the collaborative work in CYCLOPES, there may be a need for data transfer to and from our EU-partners to non-EU partners in the United Kingdom (CENTRIC, the Home Office, and College of Policing). In accordance with Art 46 (3) (a), Standard contractual clauses shall be established between the Data Controller (EU exporter) and their counterpart Data Controller (importer – third country) to stipulate the legally binding safeguards for the protection of personal data even although data shall be encrypted in-transit and at-rest.

Example of the Information Sheet

Here below is an example of the Information Sheet

Dear participant,

You are invited to participate in an interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] that is part of the Horizon 2020 EU funded project called **CYCLOPES**, Task <number of the Task> that prepares Deliverable(s) <number of the deliverable> and '<title of the deliverable>'

The task Leader is <name and organization of the Task leader>, and it is described in the project's Description of Action as follow: <add full description of the task>.

Before you decide to participate in the present interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one], please, be read carefully the following details and, if you wish, consent to your participation by filling in and signing the attached Consent Form.

What is the CYCLOPES project about?

A project to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of Law Enforcement Agencies combating cybercrime – accelerating the EU's ability to counteract growing pressures of cyber threats. CYCLOPES creates synergies between LEAs and connect industry and academia by stimulating and sustaining dialogue on pressing security matters threatening the stability of Europe and Citizen safety.

The website of the project is <https://cyclopes-project.eu>

Why have you been asked to take part?

You were asked to take part in this research activity due to your expertise and knowledge on the respective matters [or add other reason(s)].

You must be over 18 years old and not be in a situation of any vulnerability due to physical / mental conditions and/or have any perceived obligation to agree. If you are under 18 and/or perceive any pressure whatsoever to take part in this study please do not proceed further as we are not permitted to invite you to participate in this and agree to anything under such circumstances.

What will you need to do?

For the purposes of the research activity you will take part in the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] as part of <number and name of the task and/or deliverable>. Your contribution will be documented via audio recording / on paper / online [select the correct medium/media].

Any participant's personal data will be anonymised, rendered de-identified or pseudonymised securely. Only the minimum personal data justified as essential for the activity will be asked for, and its use will be strictly limited for the purpose of [insert the legal justification i.e. the purpose here, e.g. communicating personal data within the group for administrative purposes¹⁴]. All data shall be subject to strict Data Protection as planned for and monitored by the Data Controller <insert name and contact details here>.

NB! In case of any automatic data capture (if it is included in the research), it must be disclosed here as well as the legal basis of it].

Where will this take place?

This research activity will take place at <add location (or online)>.

How often will you have to take part, and for how long?

You will take part once / twice... [choose/add correct amount]. Your participation to the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] will take approximately <number> minutes/hours/days/months.

Who will be responsible for all the information when the activity is over?

The responsible of all information, including one on the Consent Form, is the organiser and/or the researcher responsible of the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one]. (See contact details below).

What will happen to the information when the activity is over?

<Add description depending on the specific conditions of each research activity>

The information on the hereby attached Consent Form will be kept securely by the researcher/Data Controller during the lifecycle of the CYCLOPES project and for a 4-year period after its completion (until: 30/04/2026) according to Article 36.1 of the CYCLOPES Grant Agreement.

¹⁴ For more details, see for example the webpages of the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman of Finland: <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/when-is-the-processing-of-personal-data-permitted> and <https://tietosuoja.fi/en/controller-s-legitimate-interests>

How will the CYCLOPES use my contribution?

As it stated above, the Task Leader / Researcher / <add correct one here> will prepare a specific report and will use participants contributions from the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one]. This report... <add description here>.

How will the CYCLOPES Consortium deal with incidental findings?

In case of any incidental findings, CYCLOPES will follow a specific policy that is described in the project's ethics deliverables.

No incidental findings are anticipated during the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one].

How long is the whole CYCLOPES research likely to last?

The duration of the project is 60 months as of May 1, 2021.

How can you find out about the results of the study?

The results of the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] will be reported by the Task leader in the context of <number of the deliverable> of the CYCLOPES Grant Agreement. According to the CYCLOPES Grant Agreement, this report is [select the correct one] publically available from the project's webpage / confidential, thus, the results are available only amongst the CYCLOPES Consortium / RESTREINT UE/EU RESTRICTED, thus available only those who have statutory authority.

Are there any foreseeable risks, discomfort or disadvantages that might arise?

There are no foreseeable risks, discomfort or disadvantages. /

There are the following risks...<description of the risks, if any>.

Are there any benefits?

<Add description of the benefits here, e.g. possibility to influence to policy, inform on needs etc.>

When will you have the opportunity to discuss your participation?

This Information Sheet and the attached Consent Form for participation in research will be provided to you before the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] and you will have time to carefully read them before deciding.

You should take sufficient time to consider the invitation and make your decision when you are satisfied that you have fully understood the nature of the research and data processing.

The project website [insert CYCLOPES website here] provides more information. However, should you require further clarification please contact the responsible organiser of this interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] [add contact details here], or the Project Data Controller [add contact details here].

What if you do not wish to take part?

Your participation is totally voluntary. You have the right to entirely or partially refuse to participate and your refusal will not disadvantage you in any way.

What if you change your mind during the study?

In that case, you are free to withdraw your consent to your participation from any part of the present activity at any time, without consequences.

Participant's data can be deleted, subject to the provisions of Art. 17 GDPR, at any time upon request. However, whilst of course we would endeavour to uphold your rights, we may face some restrictions that would apply to the above rights where data is already collected and used for research purposes.

Who is the contact person?

In case you have any questions and concerns or if adverse effects occur after this research activity you can contact <name and contact details of the researcher (both partner/legal entity and the natural person carrying out the research activity)>.

For the exercise of your rights related to data protection you may contact <contact details of the DPO> or the researcher.

Your rights in short:

You have the right to complain through your national Data Protection Authority (or by contacting the Data Controller responsible at the address provided above) about any aspect of the conduct of this consent seeking process and of course the right to accept or reject our invitation without any explanation whatsoever. However, if you decide to participate you would continue to have certain rights under the data protection law.

Your rights are:

- Withdraw your consent, for example if you opted in to be added to a participant register
- Access your personal data or ask for a copy
- Rectify inaccuracies in personal data that we hold about you
- Be forgotten, that is your details to be removed from systems that we use to process your personal data

- Restrict uses of your data
- Object to uses of your data, for example retention after you have withdrawn from a study

Please note:

Despite our collective commitment to full compliance assurance with GDPR and local data protection regulations, in the case of any unexpected data breach, were this in anyway to have exposed your data to any privacy protection risks, the respective Data Protection Officer and the Project Data Controller shall be notified in accordance with Articles 33-34-GDPR and you will be formally advised of the data affected and the preventative action taken to ensure that any breaches will be fully investigated to establish cause and prevent recurrences consistent with Art 19, 35, 17.

Example of the Consent Form

**INFORMED CONSENT FORM
FOR PARTICIPATION IN CYCLOPES' ACTIVITIES**

Hereby I, (first name, last name)

Please mark clearly your selection	YES	NO
I have read the information on this activity, i.e. the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] that will be carried out as part of Task <Task number and title> of the H2020 CYCLOPES project.		
My questions about the activity have been answered to my satisfaction, and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point.		
I understand that I am free to withdraw from the activity at any time without giving a reason for my withdrawal without any consequences to my future treatment by the researcher.		
I agree to provide information to the activity organisers under the conditions set out here and/or in the Information Sheet.		
I have been reassured that after analysis of the minimum information sought and processed, any personal data of mine shall be fully protected and deleted after the conclusion of the study.		
I consent to the information collected for the purposes of this activity, once anonymized/pseudonymised / de-identified/de-linked / (Re)identified (so that I cannot be identified), to be used for any other purposes related to the CYCLOPES project.		
I wish to participate in the interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one] under the conditions set out here and/or in the Information Sheet.		
Place:		
Date:		
Participant's signature:		

Should you have any questions, please call or write to the following contact persons	
The person responsible for this interview / survey / questionnaire / workshop [select the correct activity, or add appropriate one]:	
Name	[add here]
Organisation:	[add here]
Address:	[add here]
Phone:	[add here]
Email:	[add here]
The Data Controller of CYCLOPES:	
Name	[add here]
Organisation:	[add here]
Address:	[add here]
Phone:	[add here]
Email:	[add here]
The Coordinator of CYCLOPES:	
Name	[add here]
Organisation:	[add here]
Address:	[add here]
Phone:	[add here]
Email:	[add here]

Conclusion

The meticulous and right use of Consent Forms and Information Sheets is an integral element of a risk-averse strategy that ensures social responsibility and acceptability of the outcomes of this project. It is thus in the best interest of all consortium members as well as the participants of different activities. Following rigorously all legal and ethical requirements ensures for their part not only ethically sustainable outcomes of our project, but also ensures the market potential of any of the results in the long run too.